

Integrating Arnold Transformation with H.264 Intra Prediction for Compression

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Abstract--The impact of the Arnold transform on picture compression efficiency and quality is assessed by contrasting two methodologies: one that uses the transform and one that does not. Images are scrambled using the Arnold transform at different iteration counts to improve compressibility, with periodicity (T) considered for best recovery. Compression ratios (CR) and mean squared errors (MSE) are analyzed to determine the optimal performance measures. The results show that using the Arnold transform increases compression ratios while decreasing MSE values, indicating that it has the potential to improve both compression efficiency and image quality. Users can enter desired CR and MSE values, which allows the proposed technique to choose the right number of Arnold iterations (t) and compute $T - t$, resulting in a personalized balance between compression efficiency and image quality preservation.

Index Terms - Arnold transform, Intra prediction, scrambling algorithms, H.264 Video Codec

1. INTRODUCTION

Image compression is a critical aspect of digital media, enabling the efficient storage and transmission of images without compromising perceptual quality. By reducing the amount of data required to represent an image, compression techniques facilitate faster transmission over networks and reduce storage space [1]. [2] contributed to the field of image compression by exploring the potential of end-to-end lossy image compression methods. Unlike lossless compression, lossy compression allows for some degradation of the image quality in exchange for significantly reduced file sizes. Proper selection of algorithms in lossy compression techniques can maintain high image quality even with significant compression. The main challenge in image compression is balancing the compression ratio with image quality, ensuring the compressed image remains true to the original. The video is divided into frames, and each frame's spatial redundancy is reduced by the intra prediction algorithm in H.264.

H.264, also known as Advanced Video Coding (AVC), is a widely used video compression standard that achieves high compression efficiency by employing sophisticated prediction techniques.[3] begins with an overview of the H.264/AVC standard and the importance of intra-frame coding in achieving high compression efficiency. Ku et al. emphasizes the growing demand for high-definition video and images in consumer electronics, driving the need for efficient encoding solutions tailored for digital video and still camera applications.[4] serves as a seminal reference for understanding the technical principles, features, and benefits of the H.264/AVC standard. It underscores the transformative impact of H.264/AVC on video compression technology and its pivotal role in enabling high-quality multimedia experiences across a wide range of platforms and applications.

In the realm of video compression, intraprediction stands as a fundamental technique, playing a crucial role in reducing spatial redundancy within video frames. At its core, intraprediction involves predicting the values of pixels within a block based on neighbouring pixels within the same frame. By leveraging spatial correlations, intraprediction enables efficient compression without the need for inter-frame prediction, which involves referencing information from neighbouring frames. In this approach, the video frame is divided into smaller blocks called macroblocks, each typically consisting of a square grid of pixels, commonly arranged in sizes such as 4x4 or 8x8. Within a 4x4 macroblock, intraprediction is applied to predict the values of pixels within each 4x4 block based on neighbouring pixels [5]. H.264 supports various prediction modes and block sizes, allowing it to adapt to different image characteristics and achieve high-quality compression.[6] presents a valuable contribution to the field of video

compression by addressing the computational complexity of intra prediction mode decision. The proposed algorithm offers a practical solution for achieving real-time encoding speeds without compromising coding efficiency, thereby advancing the state-of-the-art in H.264/AVC video coding technology. In H.264/AVC, intra-prediction is a fundamental technique used in video compression, and it offers a variety of prediction modes to estimate pixel values within a macroblock. These modes are applied to different block sizes, including (4x4), (8x8), and (16x16), and they allow for efficient encoding of video frames. For (4x4), the original block (O) is a (4x4) block taken from the provided image (P0, P1 ...P8), and each of the nine intra-prediction modes generates a predicted block as in fig 1.[7] propose an improved selective encryption scheme for H.264 video that leverages intra prediction mode scrambling to enhance security while maintaining efficiency. The method offers a balance between robust protection and low computational overhead, making it suitable for real-time video applications in various multimedia contexts. When using an (4x4) macroblock, the intra-prediction modes are applied to larger blocks, resulting in larger predicted blocks. These prediction modes are essential for efficiently encoding video frames by exploiting spatial redundancy and reducing the amount of data that needs to be transmitted. Different combinations of block sizes and prediction modes are chosen based on the content and requirements of the video to achieve the best compression performance.

$$P_0 = \begin{bmatrix} P_{0_{11}} & \dots & P_{0_{14}} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ P_{0_{41}} & \dots & P_{0_{44}} \end{bmatrix}, P_1 = \begin{bmatrix} P_{1_{11}} & \dots & P_{1_{14}} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ P_{1_{41}} & \dots & P_{1_{44}} \end{bmatrix}, \dots, P_8 = \begin{bmatrix} P_{8_{11}} & \dots & P_{8_{14}} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ P_{8_{41}} & \dots & P_{8_{44}} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$O = \begin{bmatrix} O_{11} & \dots & O_{14} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ O_{41} & \dots & O_{44} \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 1. Predicted and Original 4x4 Macroblocks

Figure 2. The nine modes of operation of H.264 intra prediction

The nine modes of operation of H.264 intra prediction operation of H.264 intraprediction is noted in above fig 2. The 4x4 macroblock structure offers nine primary prediction modes, each crucial for efficiently encoding video frames. These modes encompass a range of strategies for predicting pixel values within a block based on neighbouring pixels. The vertical and horizontal modes predict values based on adjacent rows and columns, respectively, making them suitable for vertical or horizontal patterns. The DC mode calculates predictions based on the average value of neighbouring pixels, ideal for uniform areas. Diagonal modes predict values along diagonal gradients, accommodating diagonal patterns or gradients. Meanwhile, modes like vertical right and horizontal down combine vertical, horizontal, and diagonal gradients, offering versatility in encoding complex content. These modes, including vertical left and horizontal up, ensure adaptability in capturing various spatial correlations within the macroblock, ultimately contributing to efficient compression while maintaining visual fidelity. The spatial redundancy of a frame can be reduced by the intra prediction algorithm. However, by incorporating the Arnold transformation, the spatial redundancy can be further reduced. Arnold transformation is applied widely in digital image scramble because of its periodicity [8]. The Arnold transform, named after the Russian mathematician Vladimir Arnold, is a mathematical operation primarily used in the field of image processing, particularly in image encryption and scrambling. It is also relevant in the study of chaos theory and dynamical systems. This transform rearranges the pixels of an image in a deterministic manner, often resulting in a random distribution. However, the process is reversible and applying the transform a certain number of times will eventually return the image to its original form. An improved digital image scrambling method based on Arnold transform is proposed in [9]. The method can be used for the rectangle image by splitting rectangle image into several square images. Furthermore, pretreatment is added to speeding up the process and enhancing the scrambling effect. The recovering of the scrambled image depends on the reverse Arnold transform that has the same cycle of times with the Arnold transform. The recovering is lossless and need not

calculating the period of the Arnold transform. Finally, experimental results show the robustness of the method. An improved digital image scrambling method based on Arnold transform is proposed. The method can be used for the rectangle image by splitting rectangle image into several square images. Furthermore, pretreatment is added to speeding up the process and enhancing the scrambling effect. The recovering of the scrambled image depends on the reverse Arnold transform that has the same cycle times as the Arnold transform. The recovering is lossless and need not calculating the period of the Arnold transform. Finally, experimental results show the robustness of the method. [10] present a thorough analysis of a 3D Cat map-based symmetric image encryption scheme, demonstrating its robust security features and efficient performance. The chaotic properties of the 3D Cat map provide strong resistance against various types of attacks, making the scheme suitable for secure image encryption in multiple applications. [11] introduces an effective and secure image encryption scheme leveraging the combined strengths of the Arnold transform and fractional chaotic systems, providing a significant contribution to the field of image security. [12] have contributed to a significant advancement in the field of image encryption with their compact system based on Arnold transformation. Their work not only enhances the security of digital images but also ensures that the encryption process is efficient and practical for real-world applications. [13] conducted experiments to compare the effectiveness of their method with other existing scrambling techniques, demonstrating superior performance in terms of security and resistance to common attacks. The improved bit shuffling method is particularly useful in applications where robust image scrambling is required to protect sensitive visual information from unauthorized access.

Arnold Transform is defined by the following equations in 1 and 2:

$$x' = (x + y) \bmod N \quad (1)$$

$$y' = (x + 2y) \bmod N \quad (2)$$

where (x, y) are the original coordinates, (x', y') are the transformed coordinates, and N is the image dimension.

[13] discusses the implications of the Arnold transformation's period on the key space of encryption algorithms. The periodicity provides a finite yet large key space, which is essential for creating robust encryption schemes. Li and Xu compare the Arnold transformation-based scrambling with other image scrambling techniques. This work lays the groundwork for further research and development in secure image processing techniques.

1.1 Hypothesis, contribution, and organization

Hypothesis: The integration of the Arnold transform into the compression process offers promising results in terms of compression efficiency and preservation of image quality. By rearranging pixel positions before compression, the Arnold transform enhances the compressibility of the image data, leading to improved compression ratios. Furthermore, the application of the inverse Arnold transform during decompression ensures that the reconstructed image closely resembles the original input, with minimal loss of visual fidelity.

Contribution: Incorporating the Arnold transformation into H.264 intraprediction can potentially enhance compression efficiency without significant loss in image quality. By scrambling the image before applying intraprediction, the spatial correlation among pixels is altered, which might lead to more efficient prediction and quantization. This approach capitalizes on the chaotic nature of the Arnold transformation to disrupt spatial redundancy effectively, enabling H.264 to achieve higher compression ratios while maintaining image quality. Additionally, the reversible nature of the Arnold transform ensures that the decompressed image faithfully represents the original content, making it suitable for practical applications where preserving image fidelity is crucial.

The organization of the paper is structured to provide a comprehensive exploration of the integration of the Arnold transform into the compression process. Section 2 will delve into the methodology, detailing the steps and techniques used to incorporate the Arnold transform in video Codec. Section 3 will present the results and discussion, providing an in-depth analysis of the experimental outcomes. This structured organization ensures a clear and logical flow of information, facilitating a thorough understanding of the integration of the Arnold transform in video Codec.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this section, we outline the methodology for Codec, detailing the processes involved both with and without the application of the Arnold transformation. Image compression aims to reduce the storage space and transmission time of images while maintaining acceptable quality. The Arnold transformation, a scrambling technique, is sometimes used to enhance compression efficiency. We will also explain how the original image is recovered after decompression, ensuring the quality of the restored image.

2.1 Image Compression and Decompression of the proposed system (with Arnold Transform)

Figure3. Block diagram of the proposed work

The proposed work is noted in figure 3. When employing the Arnold transform into image compression, the process begins with scrambling the original image. This scrambled image then undergoes compression using techniques such as H.264 intra-prediction, where it is divided into 4X4 Macroblocks and subjected to Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) and quantization. Additionally, Huffman coding is applied to further compress the data. The Compression Ratio (CR) is calculated for one frame in the video at a time, and the corresponding t and CR values are tabulated. From this table, the iteration corresponding to the maximum CR is noted. The encoded data corresponding to the maximum CR is then used for decompression.

Recovering the image after decompression is a critical step to ensure that the original image quality is retained. This section explains the process of reading the compressed data, reversing Arnold transformation, and reconstructing the image to its original form. During decompression, the encoded data is reversed through Huffman decoding, inverse quantization, and inverse DCT, followed by the application of the inverse Arnold transform to restore the original pixel arrangement. When the iteration t equals the periodicity T, the image is fully recovered. The table reflects the periodicity for each sample input image at their respective sizes, demonstrating the number of iterations required to achieve image recovery through the Arnold transform. The following table summarizes the image sizes and their respective periodicity when using the Arnold transform. When t=T, the image recovery is achieved. This recovery process is noted for all sample input images, and the periodic values are recorded in Table1.

Table-1 Periodicity analysis of Arnold Transform

Image size	Original Image	Recoverd image after t=T	Period T
32x32		24	
64x64			48
68x68			18
128x128			96
199x199			121
256x256			192
512 X512			384
1024X1024			768

2.2 Comparison of Methodology

The workflow begins by compressing the original frames directly using the H.264 codec, and the compressed image size is recorded. The compression ratio for standard H.264 is calculated using equation 3. the compression ratio for standard is noted as CR_{std}

$$CR_{std} = \frac{CompressedImageSize}{OriginalImageSize} \quad (3)$$

The Mean Squared Error (MSE) is a measure used to quantify the difference between two images. It is calculated as the average of the squares of the differences between corresponding pixels in the original and reconstructed images. The MSE equation is given in 4.

$$MSE_{std} = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{i=0}^{M-1} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} (I_{ori}(i, j) - I_{recon}(i, j))^2 \quad (4)$$

where:

$I_{ori}(i,j)$ is the pixel value at position (i,j) in the original image.
 $I_{recon}(i,j)$ is the pixel value at position (i,j) in the reconstructed image.
 M is the number of rows (height) of the images.
 N is the number of columns (width) of the images.

This equation provides a single value that represents the average squared error between the two images, with lower values indicating better reconstruction quality.

Next, the frame is scrambled using the Arnold transform for each t from 1 to $T-1$. Each scrambled image is then compressed using the H.264 codec, and the compressed sizes are noted. The compression ratio for proposed work is calculated using equation 5. After compression, the inverse Arnold transform is applied to the compressed scrambled images to simulate reconstruction.

$$CR_{Proposed} = \frac{CompressedImageSize(Arnold+H.264\ Compression)}{OriginalImageSize} \quad (5)$$

Comparing these compression ratios highlights the impact of scrambling on compression efficiency, showing how the process of scrambling and unscrambling affects the overall compression performance of the H.264 codec. The results are compiled into a table, providing a clear comparison between the two approaches for each iteration t . The MSE is calculated between the original image and reconstructed image using equation 6.

$$MSE_{recon} = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{i=0}^{M-1} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} (I_{ori}(i,j) - I_{reconafterinverseArnold}(i,j))^2 \quad (6)$$

where:

$I_{ori}(i,j)$ is the pixel value at position (i,j) in the original image.
 $I_{reconafterinverseArnold}(i,j)$ is the pixel value at position (i,j) in the reconstructed image after applying the Arnold transform, compressing with H.264, decompressing, and then applying the inverse Arnold transform.
 M is the number of rows (height) of the images.
 N is the number of columns (width) of the images.

Figure4. Comparison Methodology

The original image frames as the initial input. These frames undergo the Arnold transform to scramble the images, aiming to boost the compression ratio (CR) is noted in figure 4. The scrambled images are then compressed using the H.264 codec. After compression, the inverse Arnold transform is applied to unscramble the images, reconstructing them closer to their original form. The Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the original and these reconstructed images is calculated to assess the quality of reconstruction. Simultaneously, the original images are directly compressed and decompressed using the H.264 codec without any scrambling. The MSE are between the original and these directly decompressed images is also calculated.

The MSE values from both methods—Arnold transform + H.264 compression + inverse Arnold transform, and direct H.264 compression—are compared. The approach yielding the lower MSE is chosen, as it indicates better reconstruction quality and lower error. This comparison helps determine whether the additional steps of scrambling and unscrambling improve compression efficiency and quality retention compared to direct compression.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: IMAGE COMPRESSION WITH ARNOLD TRANSFORM

In table2, each image undergoes H.264 Compression and Decompression. The Compression Ratio (CR) and Mean Squared Error (MSE) values are noted for each image at sizes 68x68 and 128x128. These values will later be compared with the proposed work.

Table-2 standard H.264 analysis

Image size		BARBARA	Baboon	Girl	Lena	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6
68x68	CR	3.551	4.15	3.98	3.81	3.96	4.39	3.90	3.83	4.03	4.69
	MSE	1388.89	345.88	635.36	681.00	482.12	286.67	471.42	1060.13	1042.59	283.36
128x128	CR	4.29	5.13	4.98	4.80	4.79	5.24	4.89	4.41	4.78	5.47
	MSE	865.29	367.49	342.14	480.35	365.61	252.69	300.09	1152.08	913.75	283.77

3.1 Verification

There is verification of proof of concept done for different image size and different image contents are noted in this section.

Figure5. Analysis of Compression with Arnold for S1 (68X68)

For the image S1 of size 68x68, the scrambled image at the fifth iteration, where the maximum Compression Ratio (CR) is achieved, is noted in figure 5. Additionally, the output of the inverse Arnold is recorded at the 12th iteration ($17 - 5 = 12$). Subsequently, the third image, decoded from the inverse transformation, is evaluated for Mean Squared Error (MSE) and CR, which are documented in the table below. Similarly, the same procedure is followed for the remaining images, where the scrambled images at iterations yielding maximum Compression Ratios (CRs) are noted. The outputs of the inverse Arnold transformation are then observed at corresponding iterations. Finally, the decoded images are evaluated for Mean Squared Error (MSE) and CR, and the results are recorded accordingly.

Figure6. Analysis of Compression with Arnold for Barbara (128X128)

For the image BARBARA of size 128x128, the scrambled image at the 72nd iteration, where the maximum Compression Ratio (CR) is achieved, is noted in figure 6. Additionally, the output of the inverse Arnold is recorded at the 83rd iteration ($95 - 12 = 83$). Subsequently, the third image, decoded from the inverse transformation, is evaluated for Mean Squared Error (MSE) and CR, which are documented in the table below. Similarly, the same procedure is followed for the remaining images, where the scrambled images at iterations yielding maximum Compression Ratios (CRs) are noted. The outputs of the inverse Arnold transformation are then observed at corresponding iterations. Finally, the decoded images are evaluated for Mean Squared Error (MSE) and CR, and the results are recorded accordingly.

Figure7. a and b t Vs CR analysis

The proof of concept is when we change the image size and image content, the CR values change with respect to iterations value, and it gives better values than the standard techniques is noted in figure 7.

3.2 Analysis of Proposed work

Figure8. Iterations of Arnold Transform for S1

In figure8, seventeen transformed images are noted, beginning with the original image S1 of size 68x68 as depicted in the preceding figure. "t" represents the iteration number, while "T" signifies the period. The period refers to the iteration where the original image is recovered. Importantly, it is always the case that "t" is less than "T." Arnold Transform was applied to the grayscale images for a predetermined number of iterations. The objective was to systematically scramble the image pixels in a controlled manner. Iteration counts ranging from 1 to 17 for 68x68 images and from 1 to 95 for 128x128 images were examined to assess the impact of varying levels of scrambling on compression efficiency. Additionally, each transformation undergoes a series of iterations to achieve optimal compression and subsequent decompression. These transformations are crucial for evaluating the effectiveness of the Arnold transform in preserving image quality while reducing data size. Through careful observation of the iterative process, insights into compression efficiency and the fidelity of image reconstruction can be gained. Moreover, analysing the relationship between the iteration number and the period offers valuable insights into the convergence of the compression-decompression cycle.

This table clearly demonstrates the periodic values for each sample input image, showing that the image can be recovered after decompression using the inverse Arnold transform when $t=T$. The table below presents all the input images, along with the maximum Compression Ratio (CR) obtained for a specific 't' value, as noted. The recovered images after applying the inverse Arnold algorithm are also included. Additionally, the Mean Squared Error (MSE) value corresponding to the maximum CR value is documented.

Table -3 Proposed Method analysis

Details	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	Barbara	Baboon	Lena	Girl
Original Image										
t	5	9	5	14	6	5	4	12	7	6
CR	4.79	4.99	4.55	4.6	4.8	5.42	4.29	5.01	4.53	4.71
Recovered Image										
MSE	103.7	103.2	102.4	101.4	103.46	92.4	104.4	98.36	103.72	98.64

From table3, images can be recovered after decompression using the inverse Arnold transform with T-t iterations. The table presents values for the optimal Compression Ratio (CR) and optimal Mean Squared Error (MSE) for each frame of size 68x68, with specific iterations noted. Notably, the iterations vary for each image, with one iteration producing the optimal CR and another iteration yielding the optimal MSE. The input images included S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6, BABOON, BARBARA,

GIRL, and LENA. For each image, the optimal Compression Ratio (CR) and optimal Mean Squared Error (MSE) were recorded.

Table-4 Proposed Method analysis for image size 68x68

Image size	BARBARA	Baboon	Girl	Lena	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	
68x68	t	4	12	6	17	5	9	5	14	6	5
	CR	4.29	5.01	4.71	4.53	4.79	4.99	4.55	4.6	4.8	5.42
	MSE	106.6	99.49	101.02	107.2	104.85	104.48	108.12	102.73	103.45	92.44

In terms of compression efficiency, comparison of compression ratios reveals distinct patterns between the methods. Without the Arnold transform (68x68), compression ratios range from 3.551 to 4.789, indicating varying degrees of data reduction across different images in table III. Conversely, with the Arnold transform (68x68), compression ratios range from 4.21 to 5.42, exhibiting higher ratios compared to the non-Arnold case. This suggests that the inclusion of the Arnold transform potentially enhances compression efficiency, leading to more substantial data reduction during compression.

Regarding image quality preservation, the mean squared error (MSE) serves as a critical metric. In the absence of the Arnold transform (68x68), MSE values range from 92.44 to 1388.89, with lower values indicating better preservation of image quality and less distortion from the original image. Contrastingly, with the Arnold transform (68x68), MSE values range from 92.44 to 107.203, demonstrating lower MSE values compared to the non-Arnold scenario. This implies that the inclusion of the Arnold transform tends to result in better preservation of image quality, with less distortion introduced during compression. This table4 will facilitate the comparison of CR and MSE values obtained from H.264 compression with those obtained from the proposed method. In the table below, the results of three images are documented. For each frame, all seventeen iterations were performed. The table 5 includes:

- The maximum Compression Ratio (CR) and the corresponding Mean Squared Error (MSE) values for each image.
- The iteration *t* at which the maximum CR is obtained.
- The scrambled images corresponding to the maximum CR based on *t*.

Table-5 Proposed Method analysis for different iterations

t						
	Barbara		Girl		S4	
	CR	MSE	CR	MSE	CR	MSE
1	3.28	106.50	3.51	105.34	3.69	104.55
2	3.28	105.78	3.73	107.40	3.89	103.47
3	3.91	106.46	4.02	105.55	4.3	105.59
4	4.29	106.6	4.70	98.64	4.37	102.44
5	4.13	106.48	4.46	102.95	4.38	101.45
6	4.25	104.98	4.71	101.02	4.33	104.62
7	4.12	107.41	4.26	102.17	4.31	103.75
8	3.98	105.42	4.29	102.10	4.21	101.41
9	4.01	108.03	4.41	105.24	4.42	104.56
10	4.13	106.07	4.28	106.04	4.22	101.79
11	4.04	105.49	4.33	103.09	4.16	102.23
12	4.22	104.43	4.51	101.36	4.50	104.41
13	4.05	105.84	4.48	105.12	4.54	105.25
14	4.09	106.41	4.54	103.14	4.60	102.74
15	3.42	106.38	4.08	105.42	4.47	102.07
16	3.46	105.67	3.57	108.49	4.00	104.37
17	3.50	106.92	3.71	99.87	3.85	103.54

This table highlights the iteration at which the maximum CR is achieved and the corresponding MSE value for each of the three images.

Table-6 Proposed Method analysis for image size 128x128

Image size		BARBARA	Baboon	Girl	Lena	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6
128x128	t	72	5	24	24	24	16	6	24	85	26
	CR	5.51	5.93	6.07	5.81	6.07	5.85	5.19	5.36	5.07	5.87
	MSE	106.41	102.6	101.79	106.6	105.01	103.25	102.1	102.68	104.05	92.92

The table6 presents values for the optimal Compression Ratio (CR) and optimal Mean Squared Error (MSE) for each frame of size 128x128, with specific iterations noted. Notably, the iterations vary for each image, with one iteration producing the optimal CR and another iteration yielding the optimal MSE. The input images included S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6, BABOON, BARBARA, GIRL, and LENA. For each image, the optimal Compression Ratio (CR) and optimal Mean Squared Error (MSE) were recorded. Without Arnold, the compression achieved a CR of 4.29 with an MSE of 865.29. However, employing the Arnold transform significantly improved compression, resulting in a higher CR of 5.507458 and a lower MSE of 106.4119263 at iteration T72. This indicates that the Arnold transform effectively enhanced compression efficiency and image quality for the BARBARA image. Like BARBARA, BABOON also demonstrated improved compression performance with the Arnold transform. Without Arnold, the CR was 5.13 with an MSE of 367.489, whereas with Arnold, the CR increased to 5.930323 with a reduced MSE of 102.6138 at iteration T5. This underscores the effectiveness of the Arnold transform in achieving higher compression ratios and lower MSE values for the BABOON image.

The GIRL image exhibited notable improvement in compression performance with the Arnold transform. Without Arnold, the CR was 4.98 with an MSE of 342.143, whereas with Arnold, the CR increased to 6.078842 with a significantly lower MSE of 101.7964 at iteration T24. These results highlight the substantial enhancement in compression efficiency and image quality achieved by incorporating the Arnold transform. Like other images, LENA also showed improved compression performance with the Arnold transformation. Without Arnold, the CR was 4.80 with an MSE of 480.35, while with Arnold, the CR increased to 5.810187 with a lower MSE of 106.6746 at iteration T24. This indicates that the Arnold transform effectively contributed to higher compression ratios and better preservation of image quality for the LENA image. Overall, the analysis demonstrates that the inclusion of the Arnold transform significantly enhances compression efficiency and image quality for images at a resolution of 128x128 pixels. The iterative nature of the Arnold transform optimization further improves compression performance, leading to higher compression ratios and lower MSE values compared to traditional compression methods without the Arnold transform.

4.CONCLUSION

The conducted work successfully evaluated the impact of the Arnold transform on image compression efficiency and quality. By comparing methodologies with and without the Arnold transform, it was observed that the transform leads to higher compression ratios and lower mean squared errors (MSE), indicating improved compression efficiency and better preservation of image quality. The analysis showed that scrambling images at various iterations and considering the periodicity (T) allows for optimal image recovery and enhances the compression process. The results validate the effectiveness of incorporating the Arnold transform in image compression algorithms, demonstrating its potential to achieve significant data reduction while maintaining high image fidelity. This approach provides a customizable framework where users can specify desired CR and MSE values, allowing the algorithm to select the most suitable Arnold iteration (t) and compute T-t for optimal performance. Further experimentation may refine these techniques, but the current findings highlight the Arnold transform as a valuable tool in advanced image compression strategies.

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